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Evaluating the market attractiveness for Fuel Cell micro-Cogeneration units by applying a Multi- Criteria Evaluation (MCE)

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Abstract

A market attractiveness analysis was conducted on the participation of residential fuel cell micro combined heat and power plants (FC-mCHPs) in the European grid service markets as part of the FCH-JU funded “Pathway to a Competitive European Fuel Cell micro-Cogeneration Market” (PACE) project. The aim of the analysis was to identify the most promising countries for FC-mCHP participation in grid services markets. As a number of factors of varying importance were considered in the selection process a Multi- Criteria Evaluation (MCE) approach was applied to compare alternatives and formalise a decision. In the given context, the MCE method was used to rank alternative countries based on a set of evaluation criteria that define a country’s attractiveness. Criteria were identified and then weighted based on the conducted literature research and the results of the analytical hierarchical process applied during expert interviews with FC-mCHP manufacturers respectively. This resulted in a weighted definition of market attractiveness made up of factors relating to the economic value (comprising of spark spread, self-consumption policy and market potential) and market potential (comprising of potential market size, heat demand, future policy changes, and existing installed base). **Error! Reference source not found..** For each country an overall country score was then determined. Scores were further enhanced by considering potential grid services revenues, as well as the regulations relating to market access for domestic flexibility and a high-level consideration of potential grid services revenues. The results of the MCE indicate that besides Germany, which was already proposed as a candidate by the PACE project, Belgium, the United Kingdom, Ireland and Italy currently have the highest market attractiveness for FC-mCHP’s in Europe.

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Introduction

In this paper the methodology applied in the evaluation of market attractiveness for FC-mCHP is described in detail. An analysis of the market attractiveness of residential fuel cell micro combined heat and power plants (FC-mCHPs) was conducted as part of WP 4 in the H2020 project Pathway to Competitive FC mCHP Market (PACE). Germany, as the furthest developed FC-mCHP market within the EU, was excluded from the analysis as it was already chosen for a more in-depth analysis.

By starting off with a scan of the EU-28 plus Norway and Switzerland, the countries of interest were narrowed down with the assistance of PACE members in order to identify two promising countries for further analysis. The overarching criteria used for narrowing the country selection are country-specific mCHP market conditions which were rated based on attractiveness from the view point of PACE members, and pre-defined electrical power and grid service market criteria.

A multi-criteria evaluation (MCE¹) was conducted with experts to analyse the market attractiveness of a country. An MCE is a structured approach to formalise a decision and to compare alternatives. In the given context, it was used to rank alternative countries based on a set of evaluation criteria defining their attractiveness (multi-attribute decision-making) [1]. In section 1, the methodology applied for the MCE is explained in more detail, section 2 summarizes the results of the conducted MCE and section 3 summarizes the findings.

1. Scientific Approach

The MCE was conducted following four steps. In Step 1, criteria relevant to the evaluation were defined based on literature research. In Step 2, the consortium members of the PACE project were asked to select countries from the EU-28 member states plus Switzerland and Norway that they deemed as having an attractive market, based on their professional experience and market knowledge. The selected countries were then analysed according to pre-defined criteria and assigned a numerical rating. The experts went on to assist in the weighting of the criteria using the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP)², allowing the results of the country criteria grading to be aggregated and the data to be analysed [2]. The country scores were evaluated in Step 3. Based on the data analysis, a ranking of the most promising countries was created. As a final step, the results were then validated within the consortium. Each of the steps are explained in more detail within this section.

¹ MCE is concerned with the allocation of scores to suit a specific objective on the basis of a variety of criteria that the selected countries should possess.

² AHP is a method used for pairwise comparison of elements or criteria, which are structured in defined hierarchy resulting in weights for the criteria and checking the consistency of the evaluation [11].

Step 1: Criteria Definition

Relevant criteria for the evaluation of the market attractiveness were identified and chosen based on literature research. The criteria were defined to be mutually exclusive with no correlations or dependencies, to ensure balanced grading, and to differentiate national markets. Figure 1 shows the factor tree used for the MCE. The first level comprises the criteria *Economic Value Added* (EVA) and *Market Potential for FC mCHP*.

Figure 1: Hierarchical tree of criteria considered for MCE to evaluate market attractiveness

On the second level, the sub-criteria for the EVA, which reflects the attractiveness for installing a mCHP for homeowners, is assessed based on the *Spark Spread* (difference between gas and electricity prices), existing *Self-Consumption Policies* and *Government Subsidies*.

Spark Spread

The spark spread is defined as the economic value added from producing one unit of electricity, by considering the costs for the primary fuel (natural gas) and the efficiency of the mCHP. Hence, low natural gas prices or high electricity prices are in favour of a higher spark spread. The larger the spark spread between the gas and electricity prices, the higher is the attractiveness of the technology [3] due to the added value of the produced electricity. Therefore, countries with a large spark spread add more economic value and are ranked higher.

Self-Consumption Policy

Favourable self-consumption policies improve the business case by using the electricity on site instead of feeding it back into the grid at a lower tariff. Attractive self-consumption policies improve the business case for fuel cell micro-cogeneration.

Gouvernmental Subsidies

Government support programs, such as investment support, feed-in tariffs or tax incentives allow for a decrease in investment or increase in revenue during the operation period, which leads to a higher EVA. As stated in [4] the cost of a fuel cell is much higher than traditional heating technologies and therefore requires support schemes to establish itself in the market. Therefore, countries with governmental subsidies are considered more attractive and are ranked higher.

Market Potential, as the other main criteria, is comprised of the sub-criteria *potential market size*, *heat demand*, *future policy changes* and the *installed base*, which are explained in more detail below.

Potential Market Size

An indicator for the potential market size is the market share of gas heating systems or the number of households which are connected to the gas grid. As stated in [5] future boiler market expectations are a good indicator for the potential market size for Fuel cell micro-Cogeneration.

Heat Demand

The characteristics of a typical building or climate conditions have an influence on the heat demand [6]. Those two factors have a significant influence on the annual load duration curve and hence the utilisation of the CHP unit. A higher heat demand is seen to lead to a higher attractiveness for FC mCHP.

Future Policy Changes

Policy changes can be favourable or unfavourable. Examples of a policy change in favor of CHP would be the implementation of governmental subsidy schemes or better access to aggregators to participate in the grid service market. Examples for future policy changes that disadvantage CHP are stricter CO₂ laws. Policies can have a significant impact on technology, especially one such as FC-mCHP that couples the electric and gas sector and is thus subject to both policy frameworks.

Installed base

This criterion considers the number of installations from previous and ongoing projects such as ene.field and PACE, as well as installations of conventional mCHPs. The installed base gives an indication of existing supply chains and the willingness for people to buy the technology. The higher the installed base the more attractive a country is considered.

Step 2: Expert Analysis for Country scoring and criteria weighting

One-on-one interviews with the manufacturers participating in PACE were carried out, where the participants evaluated each criterion individually, giving an overall assessment of a country's mCHP market attractiveness. Each interviewee was allowed to select a maximum of four countries which they considered to have the most attractive markets. A balanced scale³, ranging from "far below average" to "far above average" was applied to evaluate the country scoring with respect to each criterion, resulting in a numerical grading from 0 to 7. A 0 is assigned where no data is available, 1 is assigned when the grading is "far below average", and 7 is applied where the grading is "far above average" [7].

Then the relevance of each criterion was then assessed in a pairwise comparison, as shown in Table 1. In this instance, the criterion A (*EVA*) has been rated "more relevant" than criterion B (*Market Potential*), resulting in the intensity value 5.

³ A rating scale that employs an equal number of favourable and unfavourable alternatives.

Table 1: Comparison of relevance example for EVA and Market Potential criteria

Criteria A	A dominates	A much more relevant	A more relevant	A slightly more relevant	A and B equally relevant	B slightly more relevant	B more relevant	B much more relevant	B dominates	Criteria B
EVA			X							Market potential
Intensity value	9	7	5	3	1	3	5	7	9	Intensity value

Such a comparison was made for each criterion against every other criterion of the same group, also by applying a balanced scale, to transfer the ratings into *intensity* values, as seen in Table 2. The intensity values represent the relative importance of one criterion over another [8]. A weighting value is calculated considering an aggregation of each expert’s intensity value.

Table 2: Meaning of intensity values used for pairwise comparison adapted from [2]

Intensity of importance	Definition	Explanation
1	Equal importance	Two elements contribute equally to the objective
3	Moderate importance	Experience and judgment slightly favour one element over another
5	Strong Importance	Experience and judgment strongly favour one element over another
7	Very strong importance	One element is favoured very strongly over another, its dominance is demonstrated in practice
9	Extreme importance	The evidence favouring one element over another is of the highest possible order of affirmation
2,4,6,8	Intermediate values	When compromise is needed

A consistency ratio (CR) was used to check how aligned the respondents’ answers were, where the linear fit method of calculating consistency as proposed by [9] was applied (see Equation 1).

$$CR = \frac{\lambda_{max} - n}{2.7699 * n - 4.3513 - n} < 0.1 \quad \begin{matrix} \lambda_{max} & = & \text{Consistency index} \\ n & = & \text{Number of criteria} \end{matrix} \quad (1)$$

Where the maximum right eigenvalue of each studied matrix is used as a consistency index and n is the number of criteria which are compared. The CR measures how consistent the judgments have been relative to large samples of purely random judgments. If the CR is in excess of 0.1, the judgments are untrustworthy because they are deemed too random [10].

Step 3: Aggregation of the weighted scores

For each country, the scores for the criteria were multiplied by the criteria weighting and summed up, resulting in an overall country score (see equation 2). Based on this score a ranking of the countries could be created.

$$Country\ score = \sum w_i * x_i \quad \begin{matrix} w_i & = & \text{Weighting factors} \\ x_i & = & \text{Criteria scores for country} \end{matrix} \quad (2)$$

Step 4: Validation of the results

The *criteria* weighting and the selection of countries were both reviewed and accepted by the PACE team and advisory board.

2. Results

Based on the approach described in Section 1, this section presents the outcome of the country selection process based on inputs from manufacturers. Figure 2 illustrates the aggregated weights of each criterion according to the manufacturers in a factor tree.

Figure 2 MCE Factor Tree including criteria weights.

From this, the following can be understood:

- The current *economic value added* that the technology yields has more relevance or holds more weight when compared to *future market potential*
- The existence of *governmental subsidies* is the single factor of greatest concern to the manufacturers when looking to enter a market, followed closely by the *spark spread*⁴
- *Potential market size*, *heat demand* and *installed base* are seen to play a minor role in comparison to other factors.

Based on these weights, the final scores for the countries were evaluated resulting in Belgium, Italy, Ireland and the United Kingdom as the top four countries, followed by the Czech Republic, the Netherlands, France and Spain. Figure 3 illustrates the individual scores for each criterion as well as the final overall score for each of the four countries based on the manufacturers' market knowledge. Important to note is that it was made explicit by the manufacturers that their knowledge of European markets is limited to Central and Western Europe. As such, countries outside these regions were discarded. This reduced the number of countries considered by approximately half.

From the results, it can be seen that Belgium mainly profited from its favourable spark spread, a large installed base and promising future policy changes. For Ireland, the high heat demand, a large potential market size as well as favourable future policy perspectives were the main drivers for its high result. Italy has a large potential market size with a well-established gas grid, as well as self-consumption policies in place. The United Kingdom mainly profited from its installed base, the high heat demand as well as a large potential market size.

⁴ Difference between the wholesale market price of electricity and its cost of production using natural gas.

Figure 3: Spider diagrams of final four selected countries

The aim of this paper was to demonstrate a structured method to evaluating a countries market attractiveness. A multi-criteria evaluation method in combination with structured interviews was used to quantify the importance of each criterion and finally rank the countries.

The AHP process and pairwise comparison indicated that governmental subsidies, spark spread and favourable future policies are the key criteria in defining a country's market attractiveness.

As a result of the MCE Belgium, the United Kingdom, Ireland and Italy were evaluated as the countries with the highest market attractiveness for FC-mCHP within Europe.

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